

PREPARING FUTURE EDUCATORS TO FORM FRIENDLY RELATIONSHIPS IN A GROUP OF CHILDREN AS A DIDACTIC NECESSITY

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13922756>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 7th October 2024

Accepted: 9th October 2024

Published: 12th October 2024

KEYWORDS

educator, friendship,
"Brainstorming", "Magic box",
"Working in small groups",
"Cluster" methods.

ABSTRACT

The role of friendly relations in the development of adults and children, the opinions expressed by scientists in ancient times about friendship, the importance of preschool educational organization in the implementation of the educational process, help educators in the formation of friendly relations in the children's community are discussed in the article. The methods used and their effective aspects are discussed.

Introduction. Friendly relations are one of the most important human values that give meaning to human life. Friendship ties help people to achieve inner peace, awaken self-confidence, and establish relationships with others. At the heart of friendly relations are such qualities as trust in each other, similarity of thoughts, working together towards a common goal, building a relationship without any interests. In friendship, all successes and failures are shared together. A person needs a like-minded friend throughout his life, who can express his inner feelings and show him the right path in any situation. Friendly attitude of people to each other and to nature and animal world is one of the examples of our national values.

Research methodology. Friendly relations enrich people's spirituality, national values rise among people, and serve to give peace to the human spirit. Friendship ties prepare a person mentally and spiritually for the ever-expected changes. These values play an important role in making a person contribute to the development of society and find a place. Feelings of friendship were honored and appreciated by people as the highest level of human qualities. At the core of these relationships are high respect for others, trust, spiritual wealth, and brotherhood. A true friend is not defined by the occasional conversation or companionship in happy days. A true friend means to a person that he is not alone, sincere, loyal, takes friendship as the highest feeling after family, is not indifferent to his interests, is correct in any situation based on the principle of justice helps to choose a path, complements each other, is like a mirror that corrects mistakes and shortcomings.

How to make friends? There are also some rules for being friends:

- Overcoming excitement and fear;
- Communicate and express one's feelings;
- Humility;
- To behave freely;
- Learning to listen;
- Establishing a lasting relationship in any case, etc.

Some people find it difficult to establish friendships, which makes them lonely. Loneliness prevents a person from spiritual growth. A friend mainly feeds a person spiritually. Being accepted by others gives him peace and happiness, and he tries to work on himself and develop as a well-rounded and self-confident person, feeling that he is a necessary person for society.

In ancient times, in the works of Abdurrahman Jami's "Sibhatul-Abror", "Futuvvatnama sultaniya" by Husayn Vaiz Koshifi, "Mahbub-ul-Qulub" by Alisher Navoi, they described the role of friendship in human life with beautiful descriptions. The famous doctor and scientist Abu Ali ibn Sina expressed confidence that if people live in a friendly and friendly manner, they can develop their intellect at a high level and consciously know the truths of nature. He believed that people can easily get out of difficult situations if they always act as one. "Ibn Sina said to the people in the work "Risalatut Tayr" ("Treatise of the Bird"): "O brothers! Be sincere friends with each other and tell the truth. open up Let each person remove the veil of sincerity in his heart for his brother. Make it so that your brothers learn some things from you (that they do not know) and others (if they have) learn some things and perfect themselves." [5.p.20.]

Discussion. In people, friendships acquired from childhood are strong and reliable. Teaching children to make friends from kindergarten creates a comfortable environment for the development of self-confidence, calmness in a group and the ability to get along with peers without difficulty. Along with experienced pedagogues, a friend is always needed to help children acquire quality knowledge in educational institutions and to grow into a well-rounded person. Feelings of friendship develop children both morally and intellectually. In addition to education, it helps to follow the moral norms set by our society. Because education cannot be imagined without education, these two tools complement each other and occupy an equal place in human development. The formation of friendships and friendships in children from the age of kindergarten serves as a basis for them to approach school education without anxiety and fear. Formation of this attitude in children depends on the creative approach to the educational process and professional skills of the educator. In order to achieve this goal, the educator must first of all establish friendship with the child. Therefore, the educator must first of all understand the true nature of friendship. Educators appear in children's minds as ideal persons who are kind, honest, knowledgeable and able to find a solution in any situation. After the mother, the child sees the educator as the second person to rely on. Therefore, it is necessary for the teacher to justify the children's trust and organize the educational process in a high-quality way. Also, as the times are rapidly developing and we take a model from the education of foreign countries, inculcating in the minds and hearts of children that our national values are an important tool for their development, forming friendly relations with the homeland, peers, family, and nature is today's pre-school education. is one of the main tasks assigned to pedagogues of lim organizations. As a proof of this, A.S. Makarenko wrote about the role and responsibility of the pedagogue: "I am sure that educational influence can have a very powerful effect. If a person is brought up badly, I am sure that only the educators are to blame. If a child is good, he owes it to his childhood education" [6.p.16]

The fact that the educator and pedagogue sometimes makes small mistakes during the educational process has a negative effect on the education and psychology of children. Some examples of these errors are:

1. The mistake of working with each child individually, that is, paying attention to individuality. An equal approach to children with different character traits can cause them nervousness, indifference to the training process, and boredom with the place of education. He struggles to show his abilities.
2. Repeating the child's mistakes. As a result of highlighting the child's mistakes, he feels humiliated and guilty in front of his peers, and his self-confidence decreases. This process

becomes a habit during the child's growing up period, he is afraid to express his opinion and make independent decisions in the future.

3. Educators' lack of emotional approach to their profession. Children expect not only teaching, but also affection and attention from the teacher. A teacher's emotional indifference or disregard for children's feelings can make them feel uncomfortable and insecure.

4. Strict discipline or excessive entertainment. The teacher's strict adherence to discipline in the training process limits the children's freedom, hinders them from the spiritual and intellectual side in acquiring knowledge and learning, and excessive excitement causes chaos and disrespect for others in children.

5. Ignoring uniformity. The educator does not allocate the same time to all children, or does not direct his attention equally. Such situations cause children to have negative thoughts about each other and the teacher.

6. Not listening to children. The teacher's indifference to children's wishes, not listening to their words, considering their opinions unimportant causes children to feel superfluous and unaccepted. The child suffers mentally in such a situation.

In order not to make the above mistakes, the teacher must acquire professional knowledge, approach the educational process from a pedagogical and psychological point of view, and work on himself. It is useful to use the help of other children in solving the problems observed in the child. Because sharing various psychological processes with a friend who supports them makes him feel calm. A child needs friendships for the following reasons

Future educators are recommended to use methods and pedagogical technologies together with fairy tales, poems, stories, various games to form friendly relations between children.

"Brainstorming" method. This method is used by the teacher after explaining the topic of the new activity to the children in order to know how well they have mastered the topic and what kind of imagination they have formed. For example, a teacher conducts training on the topic of friendly relations with children. Asks a general question to the children and accepts the answer given by each child without discussion. With the help of this method, children can learn about the problems they face in making relationships and making friends and find ways to overcome them. The teacher raises the following questions: "What qualities do you need to have in order to be a good friend?" and others. Children's answers are all listened to, and at the end of the method, the answers are summarized and the final result is obtained. Defects in children's thinking are eliminated.

"Working in small groups". Before using this method, the educator gives information to the children about what they should do, explains through examples. To carry out the method, children are divided into small groups of 5-6 people. Pictures are distributed to them depicting the processes of several children working, playing football, and teaching. Each small group consults with its peers about the given picture, names the children depicted in the picture as their friends and makes up a story in turn. One child starts the story and the others continue one after the other. The teacher tells the children that they should listen to the opinion of each participant with respect, respect themselves and their friends, and follow the rules. Children control themselves so as not to have difficulty in continuing the process by carefully listening to their group mates, and use feedback to connect the sequence of events.

Through the "magic box" method, the educator uses the children to form a friendly relationship with nature. First of all, the educator teaches children about the role of nature in people's lives, the need to preserve nature, and to be friendly. At the end of the training, this method is used in order to know the level of children's assimilation of new knowledge. The method is carried out in the following order: the teacher puts pictures of different types of trees and birds on the blackboard, tells the children to choose the pictures from the boxes that belong to the above and stick them under them. The child interprets each picture chosen by himself. For example; trees turning green and yellow, giving people coolness, supplying people with fresh air, fruits growing on them, etc.; pictures of different birds, laying eggs, cleaning nature from harmful insects. The given pictures teach children to reason and make the right choice, to make independent decisions.

"Cluster" method. It is recommended to apply this method to children who cannot adapt to the group and have low self-confidence in order to motivate them, overcome their fears, instill self-confidence, respect for their teammates, and initiative. Before using the method, the teacher talks with the children about the new child, explains that their help is needed to attract him to the group and make friends. The teacher expresses warm thoughts about the new child, and asks the children to continue these thoughts. During the method, the educator invites the new child to the blackboard, and the educator and the children jointly describe his positive qualities, the teacher draws a cluster diagram on the blackboard, writes the name of the new child in the center, and writes the definitions given to him and sticks asterisks around the new child. by hearing positive comments from others about him, his fears begin to recede, his self-confidence appears, he develops affection towards his peers, and he finds strength in himself in establishing relationships with other children.

Conclusion. In short, the formation of friendly relations between children is one of the most important processes. The teacher's deep mastery of professional skills, creativity, ability to correctly assess the situation, patience and generosity are useful in the implementation of quality educational process in preschool educational organizations. Today, forming friendships among children is a very important process for their future. Making the right decisions, choosing the right methods and technologies in this way depends on the skills of the teacher.

References:

1. *Mirzayeva D.Sh.* Maktabgacha pedagogika. O'quv qo'llanma.- Toshkent, 2022. – 147 b.
2. *Nishonova Z., Alimova G.* Bolalar psixologiyasi va uni o'qitish metodikasi. – Toshkent: O'zbekiston Yozuvchilar uyushmasi Adabiyot jamg'armasi nashriyoti, 2006. – 160 b.
3. *Norbosheva Mehri* "Bolalar psixologiyasi" Ma'ruza matnlari. Toshkent-2002.-89 b.
4. *Sodiqova Sh.* Maktabgacha pedagogika. – Toshkent: "Tafakkur bo'stoni", 2013. – 288 b.
5. QADRIYATLAR FALSAFASI MODULI DASTURI (O'QUV USLUBIY MAJMUA) f.f.d B.Talapov Namangan – 2023.- 216 b
6. *Hasanboyeva O.U* Maktabgacha ta'lim pedagogikasi. Pedagogika kolejlari uchun qo'llanma. 3-nashr. Toshkent-"Ilm Ziyo"-2012.- 186 b
7. *Yuldasheva G.S* "Shaxslararo munosabatlar psixologiyasi" moduli bo'yicha o'quv-uslubiy majmua. Toshkent pedagogika universiteti. 2018-131 b
8. <http://zuxra-urganch.zn.uz/> 2.10.2024

9. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/zamonaviy-ta-lim-metodlari-ta-lim-samaradorligi-kafolati/viewer> 3.10.2024
10. B.T.JURAYEV PEDAGOGIK VA PSIXOLOGIK FANLARNI O'QITISH METODIKASI. O'quv qo'llanma "FAN VA TA'LIM" Buxoro-2022

